

Effectiveness of Roselle Kombucha as Anti-Hypercholesterolemic in Male Mice

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Biological science continues to develop over time and it is possible if the fields of biological science are combined in a research. This research covers two fields of biological science, namely microbiology and animal physiology. Microbiology is the study of microbes or microorganisms. Microbiology is a branch of science from biology and requires supporting sciences of chemistry, physics, and biochemistry. Microbiology is often called the practical science of biochemistry (Pelczar *et al.*, 1986). One of the processes carried out by microbes is fermentation. Through fermentation, process products can affect the physiological processes of animals. Physiology is a science that discusses the physiological functions of living things, how the process so that animals can maintain their existence can also be said to be a science that studies the processes and activities that occur in the animal body. A more modern definition states that physiology is a science that studies homeostasis and the control mechanisms that take place to achieve and maintain homeostasis. Homeostasis is the term used by a physiologist (Wlater B. Canon 1871-1945) to denote the existence of stability that is maintained in the body of an organism despite many factors that may alter that stability. The merging of these fields of biology will be very helpful in maximizing new research results because the studies provides various benefits, including increasing research productivity and quality (Yustina and Damardi, 2017).

The roselle plant which has the scientific name *Hibiscus sabdariffa* belongs to the Malvaceae family. Roselle can grow well in tropical and subtropical climates. Native habitat in areas that stretch from India to Malaysia. But now this plant is widespread in the tropics and subtropics around the world. Therefore, it is not surprising that this plant has different common names in different countries. For example in England Roselle, red sorel, in Malaysia asam susur, in Thailand kachieb priew, in North Africa it is known as carcade (Maryani and Kristiana, 2005). The shape of a flower produced by a plant morphologically consists of sepals, petals, stamen, carpel all of which originate from the receptacle or flower base (Abidin, 1984). Roselle flowers are known to have many benefits for the community. We know that tea is extracted from the petals of the roselle flower (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*). This type of tea can be made into kombucha by fermenting roselle extract using the role of microbes in kombucha fermentation. Roselle kombucha can be used as an alternative to chemical drugs to lower cholesterol levels. Therefore, this study aims to determine and analyze the capability of roselle kombucha in lowering blood cholesterol in male mice (*Mus musculus*).

Hypercholesterolemic is a condition characterized by increased levels of cholesterol in the blood exceeding the normal threshold (Frinanda, 2014). One of the causes of hypercholesterolemia is unhealthy eating patterns, especially the tendency of people to consume fast food, for example, fried foods. Fried foods can be dangerous if cooking oil is

used repeatedly. Fadilah (1999) explained that vascular atherosclerosis with clinical manifestations in the form of heart disease and stroke is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in both developed and developing countries. Hypercholesterolemia caused by high levels of cholesterol in the blood (Durrington, 2003), is not a disease, but is metabolic system damage and can be a secondary cause of several types of disease and contributes to several forms of the disease, especially cardiovascular disease (Grundy et al., 1998). The active compounds contained in roselle include organic acids (hydroxycitric acid and hibiscus acid), anthocyanins, polysaccharides (pectin), and flavonoids. Roselle extract can reduce levels of LDL-C, VLDL-C, total cholesterol and lipid peroxidation, triglycerides and can increase levels of HDL-C. Some compounds that are thought to have a cholesterol-lowering effect are anthocyanins and flavonoid derivatives. The important content contained in roselle petals to reduce cholesterol levels is the content of pectin, β -sitosterol, and anthocyanins but the effect of reducing total cholesterol is mainly influenced by pectin and anthocyanins. Scientific research that examines the effect of consumption of roselle on cholesterol is still limited. Most of the existing research uses roselle extract, while the general public consumes roselle by brewing it like making tea. So the researchers wanted to know to what extent the effect of roselle kombucha can reduce cholesterol levels in mice (Wahyuni, 2016 in Suhartatik *et al.*, 2009).

Kombucha is an antioxidant drink. The antioxidants in kombucha come from compounds present in the basic ingredients of kombucha tea. kombucha is a fermented drink made from a solution of tea and sugar using a kombucha starter that is fermented for 14 days. Fermentation can take place if the sugar content as a carbon source is sufficient. The breakdown of sugar molecules by kombucha microbes takes time. The longer the fermentation process, the more carbon sources run out and the higher the acidity, resulting in a slow and stop fermentation process (Nur *et al.*, 2018). According to Fardiaz, (1992) that bacterial growth is influenced by nutrients, pH, water, oxygen, and growth-inhibiting compounds. Sugar (sucrose) will be broken down into glucose and fructose by the bacteria found in kombucha. each organism has a certain pH range that is still possible for growth and also an optimum pH. Furthermore, Frank (1991) added that kombucha fermentation was influenced by several environmental factors such as the amount of inoculum (seedling), incubation temperature, pH, initial sucrose content, and assisted by yeast culture and acetic acid bacteria. This is also supported by Buckle (1987) in Nurmiati *et al.* (2017), the main factors affecting the growth of microbes are nutrients, temperature, water, and oxygen (especially for aerobic microbes).

Kombucha fermentation is the activity of *Acetobacter xylinum* and the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *A. xylinum* bacteria are obligate aerobes capable of synthesizing a layer of cellulose attached to the microfibrils that make up nata (cellulose) so that they come into contact with oxygen. Acetic acid bacteria convert glucose into gluconate, and fructose into acetic acid (Balentine et al., 1997). Sitompul (2003) added that antioxidants through their

mechanism can inhibit and prevent LDL damage due to oxidation, which in turn can reduce cholesterol levels in the blood. Roselle kombucha will experience a decrease in antioxidant activity even though it is very small after being fermented for 1 day. According to Suhartatik et al. (2006), the fermentation process of sweet tea solution into kombucha will reduce its antioxidant activity. The decrease in antioxidant activity of kombucha from roselle flower petals tends to be less than the decrease experienced by kombucha from black tea (*Camellia sinensis*). Although there was a decrease in antioxidant activity, the antioxidant activity of kombucha roselle was still relatively high when compared to kombucha from tea leaves (down by 85% after fermenting for 10 days). According to Suhartatik et al. (2006), fermenting tea into kombucha will increase its antioxidant activity until the 3rd day of fermentation, while kombucha is made with variations of tea bags and mixed teas will provide different antioxidant activities. Infused tea bags will have greater antioxidant activity than blended tea, but their antioxidant activity during fermentation will decrease drastically when compared to blended tea (Suhartatik and Kurniawati, 2008). Karyantina (2008) also stated that the antioxidant activity of kombucha would not affect if the initial medium (sweet tea brew) was made with different types of sugar. Currently also known tea from roselle flower petals (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*). Roselle tea can be made by brewing 2-3 dried roselle petals with 200 mL of hot water. Roselle tea is also efficacious as an antioxidant drink and as an antihypertensive. A researcher from Thailand has tested roselle to lower cholesterol in mice. The results showed that serum cholesterol decreased by 22% for 500 mg/kg roselle extract and 26% for 1000 mg/kg weight. Decreases also occurred in serum triglycerides by 33% and 28% and serum low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels as much as 22% and 32% (Vitriani, 2007).

Based on the explanation above, to take benefit of functional properties of roselle and the capacity of microbes to ferment kombucha to produce compounds that could decrease cholesterol, it is hoped that functional drinks roselle kombucha will be obtained that have dual functions for support body health as anti-hypercholesterolemic. The collaboration between two fields studies of biological science can produce quality scientific works and can increase the knowledge and capabilities of researchers because of the transfer of knowledge. Therefore, collaboration in research of several fields in biological science needs to be maintained and improved because it is useful in disseminating information and developing science. To find out more representative research in the field of microbiology and animal physiology resources, it is necessary to carry out further studies in periodicals.

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